

E-content development for Ainkurunuru resource in ta.Wikisource

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Abstract

Tamil Wikisource is one of the schemes of Wikimedia Trust enabling the online Library scheme. This serves as a platform offering free content (Shared License) Books with their original sources in the digital medium. This scheme provides the Contributors of this site to upload books of their own interest, make corrections, upgrade the existing ones and also opportune for the exchange of feedback with respect to constructive growth of the platform. This scheme is successfully used in 72 languages. This scheme of Wikisource under Tamil language has more than 2468 books. This covers a herculean 3.5 lakh pages and more in it. This Covers books from Sangam Literature, Bhakthi Literature, Literature from the countryside (Folk tales or Folktales), History, Science, Arts, Grammar, Travelogues and Biographies. Sangam Literature which is called as the oldest form of literature from Tamil language has very minimal information and data under its belt. The books associated with Aynkurunooru, which is a part of Sangam Literature, has only 5 books as relevant sources and data relating to the original source. The authenticity of the association of those 5 books with Aynkurunooru is also verified. Also there arises the question on the number of secondary sources and data associated with cand what shall be the answer to it. Should one not think about updating this worrying factor to a positive solution? Is it not time bounding to identify at least the free licensed books related to Ainkurunuru through this study? These shall be addressed in this research paper. This separation or gap shall be brought to limelight by accumulating and identifying the books that are printed and books that are in the various stages of its publication. Studies like these would accumulate sufficient data and information pertaining to linguistics and result in further development of knowledge. This accumulation shall serve as the data and information required for the origin of research in cognitive technology and Nature of Languages. Hence, this research paper aims at listing the sources associated with Ainkurunuru that are not a part of Tamil Wikisource, the guidelines of adding the same list of sources in the platform and it's acknowledging the importance of these sources in Tamil Wikisource platform.

Keywords: Wikisource, Ainkurunuru Tamil Nature Languages processing, Python Language.

Introduction

Enriching the data and information about Tamil Language in the E-platform of Wikisource is the primary objective of Tamil enthusiasts. It is the responsibility of the contemporaries to safeguard the literary text of Ainkurunuru by updating it in digital platforms and preserve it as our ancestors have done throughout history. The current study aims at ensuring the documentation as digital content and guidelines for updating all the available data and information about Ainkurunuru on the basis of Tamil literary history in the Wikisource platform.

Significance of Ainkurunuru

Ayungurunorru is a part of EttuThogai Books from Sangam Literature. This book was written during the later part of Sangam Age (2nd Century AD). This book comprises 100 poems for each of the five different types of landforms including Kurunju, Mullai, Marudham, Neidhal and Palai respectively making it a collection of 500 poems.

Ainkurunuru deals with poems of Agaporul nature and hence the poems have the themes of love, happiness, sorrow, separation, longingness and redemption. The poems are delicately structured with simpler form and are highly rich in imagination. These traits make Ainkurunuru a prototype representing the poems of Agaporul Poems. Some of the significant features of Ainkurunuru are as follows

- Important collection in Tamil literature dealing with the themes of love, happiness, sorrow, separation, longingness and redemption.
- The poems are constructed with rich imagination and are simpler in form.
- This is an example of exemplary wealth beheld by Tamil language and the vastness of Tamil literature.
- The style with which the poems are written is eloquently natural, making use of the words from contemporary life. The Diction used in these poems are colloquially used by people.
- The Poems delve on the customs, tradition and cultural practices of Tamil society. This also acts as the best form of documentation registering the life of Tamil people.
- The poems of this book played a major role in the growth and development of Tamil literature.
- One of the significant features of Ainkurunuru is the nuances with which Agathinai poems are composed. The poems are filled with literary devices like Metaphor, Ullurai, and Iracichi.
- Metaphor is referring to the objective of an object in a concealed manner.
- Simile is the comparison of one object with another.
- Iracichi, Ullurai is exhibiting the true nature of the object.

- All the three traits mentioned above are evidently visible in Ayubgurunooru.
- Yet another distinct feature of Ainkurunuru is its depiction of lifestyle, culture and tradition of the people of its age.
- The poem comprises themes of love, valour, motherhood, fatherhood, friendship, virtue and charity. This proves effective in understanding the life of the people of that time.

Ainkurunuru is considered as one of the important books of Tamil literature. The poems in this book highlights the tradition and prosperous life of Tamil people. The poems of this book prevail as a significant part of Tamil literature till date. Some of the important poetic lines from such glorified Ainkurunuru are as follows: -

Kurinji thinai - "மலர்க் கொடி இனிய நெஞ்சம் மெல்லத் தூங்கும்"

மலர்க் கொடி இனிய நெஞ்சம் மெல்லத் தூங்கும்"மலர்க் கொடி இனிய நெஞ்சம்
மெல்லத் தூங்கும்"

""மலர்க் கொடி இனிய நெஞ்சம் மெல்லத் தூங்கும்"

Mullai thinai - "அன்னம் வாழியோர் எம் அன்னம்"

அன்னம் வாழியோர் எம் அன்னம் "அன்னம் வாழியோர் எம் அன்னம்"

" "அன்னம் வாழியோர் எம் அன்னம்"

Marutham thinai - "பூங்கொடிப் பொழில் பூத்தது"

பூங்கொடிப் பொழில் பூத்தது "பூங்கொடிப் பொழில் பூத்தது"

" "பூங்கொடிப் பொழில் பூத்தது"

Neithal thinai - "மணல் தார் மணல் தார் மணல் தார்"

மணல் தார் மணல் தார் மணல் தார் "மணல் தார் மணல் தார் மணல் தார்"

" "மணல் தார் மணல் தார் மணல் தார்"

Palai thinai - "நெஞ்சே நீ சினந்து ஏன்" [11].

நெஞ்சே நீ சினந்து ஏன் "நெஞ்சே நீ சினந்து ஏன்" [11].

" [11]. "நெஞ்சே நீ சினந்து ஏன்" [11].

The poems of Ainkurunuru were written as manuscripts in palm leaves right from the later part of Sangam age. When time posed a threat of its destruction, Tamil scholars transferred them to print media and published them as books.

The primary text of Ainkurunuru was published in 1903 in Chennai. This was revised and published by U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer. He meticulously looked into many manuscripts and published the version of the book in such a way that it would benefit even the people of the present age.

After Saminatha Aiyer, It was S. Vaiyaburi Pillai who published Ainkurunuru in 1927.

He made revisions from the version published by Saminatha Aiyer and included much new information that was put forth in the latest edition.

In 1970, Tamil Literary Renaissance Association published Ainkurunuru. This edition was published by Professor Avvai Duraisamy. He made revisions to the version of Vaiyaburi Pillai and put forth new opinions and information.

In 2003, Tamil University published Ainkurunuru. This was published by Professor M. Sivasubramanian. This edition published by him contained much more detailed explanations than that of the previous editions of Ainkurunuru.

All the above five editions of publications concentrated on collectively organisation of poems, structure and formation of poems, types of poems, grammar and meaning after studying everything in detail. All these serve as an important form of information documented from studies and research in Tamil literature.

A brief note on the history of publication of Ainkurunuru can be projected as follows.

- 1903: Publication by U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer
- 1927: Publication by S. Vaiyaburi Pillai
- 1970: Publication by Tamil Literary Renaissance Association
- 2003: Publication by Tamil University

All these publications have detailed explanations for Ainkurunuru that are important for the references of future scholars and researchers in Tamil literary history.

Ainkurunuru in Print Media

U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer, in 1903 organised Ainkurunuru in the following order of Marutham, Neidhal, Kurunji, Paalai and Mullai with each section consisting of hundred poems and published in printed form. The second and third editions of the same were published in the year 1920 and 1944 respectively. The Manuscripts of Thiruvaduthurai Adheenam, K. M. Veluppilai and Thirumayilai Sanmugam Pillai enabled the preservation of comments and criticisms, also with Alvaar Thirunagari T. Latchumana Kavirayar's older textul manuscripts helped in this publication.

Avvai. Su. Duraisami Pillai's explanation for the first hundred poems of Ayubgurunooru was published by Ka. Govindan in 1938. After that Annamalai University published Marudham, Neidhal as a volume and later Kurunji, Paalai as a compilation and Mullai as a separate volume. Thus published Ainkurunuru as compilation three volumes in 1957. This publication was supported by the edition of U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer and manuscripts of Seerkazhi Govindasami reddy. P. V. Soma Sundaranaar's explanatory text was published by Saiva Siddhanta Publishing corporation in 1961. The revised edition of the same was published in 1966.

Primary source publication of Ainkurunuru

- Ainkurunuru (original version) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1957

- Ainkurunuru Kurinji (original version) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1957
- Ainkurunuru Mullai (original version) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1958
- Ainkurunuru Marutham (original version) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1938
- Ainkurunuru (Marudham, Neithal) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1957

Versions with original text and explanation

- Ainkurunuru and older texts – Dr. U. Ve. Saminatha Iyer, 1903
- Original version of Ainkurunuru and its explanation - Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1938
- Ainkurunuru - Dr. U. Ve. Saminatha Iyer, 2012
- Ainkurunuru Mullai – Puliyoor Kesigan, 2010
- Ainkurunuru – Print publication, 1994
- Ainkurunuru- Dr. S. Jegathratchagan, 2017

Versions of Text

- Ainkurunuru and older texts- Dr. U. Ve. Saminatha Iyer, 1903
- Original version of Ainkurunuru and its explanation - Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1938
- Ainkurunuru (Original version)- Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1957
- Ainkurunuru Mullai (Original version)- Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, First edition 1958
- Ainkurunuru Marutham (original version) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1938
- Ainkurunuru (Marudham, Neithal) – Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai, 1957

After the publication of the first edition by U. Ve. Sa, the second edition was published in 1920. After his publication Avvai. Su. Duraisamy Pillai's version of publication was made as three volumes in 1957. The first hundred poems were published before the publication of the three volumes in 1938. Finally, Avvai. Su. Duraisamy Pillai compiled all the volumes in 1958 and published them as the publication of Annamalai University. Subsequently Po. Ve. Somasundaranaars's explanation was published in 1961 and 1966. The original version/ source was published by N. C. P. H in 1957 and Murray's edition of publication was released in 1981.

Translation of Ainkurunuru

Ainkurunuru (Selected Poems of Love) in English – Dr. S. Rajeswari (Section: Sangam Tamil Poems- English translation list, Publisher: Sandhirodayam, Madurai, Year: 2022).

AINKURUNURU IN ENGLISH - S.N. KANDASWAMY, TAMIL UNIVERSITY, THANJAVUR.

Malayalam Translation

The Poems of Ainkurunuru have been translated to Malayalam language thrice.

The work titled "Rendaiyira Varsathe Trinjyitta Malayalam Padhyangas' ' was published by Vettam Maani as editor-in-chief composed of poems written by Orambogiyar, Peyanar and Kabilar. The poems of Ainkurunuru are also found in "Agam Kavidhaigal " which was edited and translated by N. V. Krishnna Warriar.

Editions of Ainkurunuru

Dr. U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer

The poems of Ainkurunuru have been written and used right from the lateral part of Sangam Age. This was later revised, edited and published for the first time in 1903 by Dr. U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer in such a way for the Tamil people of present age to be benefitted out of it. Once after the publication of this book, many Tamil scholars have released secondary texts for this book.

Even though the book of Ainkurunuru was published in 1903, the history of the secondary text on this book can be traced back to 1938 from Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai. The secondary texts primarily started with Maruthathinai and later on 18 texts have originated. U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer, in both his versions in 1903 and 1920 respectively, has attached the old text along with it during its publications. This old text was mentioned to be a part of a manuscript by Alwar Thirunagari Sri T.Lakshmana Kavirayar by U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer. There are 196 poems in the old text. In the text Vezhappathu, Vellankurukkuppathu, Siruvenkakaippathu, Kezhappathu, Kurakuppathu have been acquired without any discrepancies. Whereas the secondary text of 13 chapters is not found. Other than this the old texts of a few smaller poems have been obtained.

Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai

His version of publication published by Annamalai University consisted of notes on the biography of authors of each Thinaï along with the distinguished themes about global science and philosophy. Also, the old text, hidden moral and difference in subject of each poem is properly arranged. The details of the secondary texts cited by him were also provided in the respective pages. He pointed out the same subject difference as mentioned by U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer. After the version published by U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer, it was this edition published by Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai which was highly regarded and as the best form of revised version. Even the line missing from the 490th poem of U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer's publications were found, rectified and fulfilled in the publication of Avvai S.Duraisamy Pillai.

Palm leaf manuscripts

Doctoral Dissertations

The poems of Ainkurunuru were originally composed on palm leaf manuscripts during the later part of the Sangam Age. Dr. U. Ve. Swaminatha Iyer undertook the task of revising, editing, and publishing these poems for the first time in 1903. Following the publication of this book, numerous Tamil scholars subsequently released additional texts related to Ainkurunuru.

The palm leaf manuscripts are being preserved in the following places.

Adayar Library and research centre, Chennai.

Annamalai University, Chidambaram.

Institute of Asian Studies, Semmanjeri, Chennai.

Adi Bhimaraja Goswami Mutt, Thanjavur.

Ramanasramam. Thiruvannamalai.

World Institute of Tamil Studies, Taramani, Chennai.

Oriental Manuscripts Library, Chepauk, Chennai.

Oriental Manuscripts Library, Thiruvananthapuram.

Dr. U.Ve. Swaminatha Iyer Library, Thiruvanmiyur, Chennai.

Tamil University, Department of Manuscripts, Thanjavur.

Doctoral Dissertations

- Ainkurunuru – Syntax Bibliographies, Dr. S.Silambumani
- Ainkurunuru Statement and Old Text - Semantics Dr. Bhavani
- A comparison of the values of the women living in Ainkurunuru and Kalithogai - Mrs. G.Karthika

Ainkurunuru in Wikisource

There are two books available on Wikki source regarding Ainkurunuru. One of them is integrated with the original source, while the other exists as a standalone text in draft form. No specific source is attributed to the latter [1]. On December 30, 2023, the presence of two books was confirmed [6]. However, it is noted that few more updates are still required, as indicated by the mentioned references. With the future in mind, one should explore methods to refine and enhance the books currently present or to be created on Wikki source.

Improving tabulation of Ainkurunuru

Documents written on the basis of Ainkurunuru should not be confined to printed books. Hence, the inclusions that are mandatory in the tabulation of the book shall be constructed as follows.

- Ainkurunuru in Palm leaf manuscripts
 - Primary and original source manuscripts
 - Explanatory and secondary manuscripts
- Ainkurunuru as printed book
 - Primary Text
 - Secondary Text

- Old texts
- Textuality
- Contemporary texts
- o Theses
 - Comparative research of Indian languages
 - Comparative research of foreign languages
 - Comparative research of dravidian languages
 - Comparative research on the comparison of Tamil literature.
- o Translations
 - Translation in Global languages
 - Translation in Indian languages

Tabulations of this sort shall strive for ages to come. The analysis of this shall be attempted.

Significance of updating Ainkurunuru

Wikisource serves as a collaborative platform for consolidating educational resources, as it significantly contributes to the conduct of research related to the natural language of Tamil. This platform not only facilitates studies in linguistics but also serves as a medium for researchers from various global universities to conduct and disseminate their research. Some of the best outcomes of Wikisource are,

- To continue striving for various research areas in Ainkurunuru.
- For facilitating comparative research on Indian languages.
- For facilitating comparative research on Global languages.
- For accumulation of data in research based on linguistic grounds.
- For creating words from Ainkurunuru in Wiktionary schemes.
- For conjoining Wikidata.
- For the creation of new essays and articles in Wikipedia.
- For the creation of instrumentation that enables the distribution of information regarding Ainkurunuru.
- For the creation of new software on Ainkurunuru.
- For instrumentation of teaching learning methodology of Ainkurunuru.

Conclusion

Based on the current study, it can be concluded that the Tamil Wikisource will be a repository library that will store studies on Ainkurunuru and freely licensed books relevant to it in one place. Moreover, it arranges that the Tamil Wikisource Project will be a forerunner

for all the 72 Wikisource projects and that the Wikisource project will improve on the basis of the history of Tamil literature.

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